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INTERNET INFLUENCE ON WORLDVIEW OF YOUTH

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ABSTRACT. *The aim of this article is to view the Internet influence on worldview of modern youth and to determinate its place in the process of communication. The Internet is an increasingly important part of everyday life for people around the world. But if you've never used the Internet before, all of this new information might feel a bit confusing at first. Throughout this tutorial, we'll try to answer some basic questions you may have about the Internet and how it's used. When you're done, you'll have a good understanding of how the Internet works, how to connect to the Internet, and how to browse theWeb.*

Keywords: *vale ology; influence of the Internet; communication; socialization; modern youth; worldview; advantages and disadvantages of the Internet.*

INTRODUCTION.

The Internet is quite a strong effect on everyone, especially teenagers. Modern schoolchildren believe that they can no longer study without the Internet. To study this issue, a sociological survey was conducted among students of several classes of our gymnasium.

We learned what the Internet is quite a long time ago. Yes, of course, the Internet is the greatest and most amazing invention of the last century, with the help of which humanity made a huge leap into the future, gave an incentive to progress. The Internet simplifies our lives, opens up more and more opportunities for us. It is also a great help in your studies and work. Now you can get any information you need on a given topic at a moment's notice, and get in touch with anyone in the world in a matter of seconds.

The Internet is a great discovery that gives us great opportunities. But as I became more familiar with the Internet, I realized that not everything that seems good is good. I think many people will agree with me that there is a lot of information on the Internet that cannot be read or even seen, especially by the younger generation! Children stop reading books, the circle of communication of teenagers is reduced: they are limited to virtual communication in chat rooms and forums, young people are rapidly growing aggressiveness, which is caused by excessive and sometimes painful passion for computer games. All this leads to a gradual degradation of the individual.

What is the Internet? "The Internet is a global computer network that provides huge freedoms to users" - one of the official formulations. The Internet is a computer network also known as the "world wide web". You no longer need to go to the cinema, to a concert of your favorite band, to linger in the library, to bother shopping, you can get all the information you need without leaving the screen of Your monitor.

For many teenagers, the Internet is a means of entertainment, and only then a source of knowledge and an assistant in their studies. Very few teenagers use computers and the Internet for educational purposes. By participating in virtual communities, children can easily communicate, find new acquaintances, and exchange information.

METHODS AND MATERIALS.

The Internet is an ambiguous phenomenon, and just as ambiguous is its impact on teenagers. It is bad because it has no boundaries! That is, it does not protect teenagers from profanity that children do not need to know at all. Along with useful information and positive communication, there are clubs of drug addicts, suicides, terrorists, a sea of pornography, which is a huge danger for teenagers who have not yet formed moral values, and the craving for "adult" entertainment is great. In the absence of proper control on the part of adults, young people in the social network become the object of negative information and psychological influence, manipulation. It is not uncommon for young people to be used as a tool of informational confrontation, to be involved in mass protest actions. A particular danger for children is the possibility of involving them through social networks in extremist groups, destructive religious organizations, whose activities are aimed at committing anti-social, illegal, including criminally punishable acts.

The influence of the Internet on young people is one of the factors that shape the psychological development of young people and their perception of the world as a whole. In the modern world, a person can no longer imagine life without a phone, laptop, tablet and, of course, the Internet. The progress of technology has covered a large part of our living space. We ourselves sometimes do not notice how much time we spend on the Internet, setting an example to our curious generations. Number of users

The Internet is growing rapidly, and the proportion of people under the age of 18 and older among users of the world wide web is very large. For many people, especially young people, the Internet is becoming an information and educational environment, without which they cannot imagine life.

However, a large percentage of information that is freely accessible, leads to the denial of worldviews based on certain moral or ethical norms. In this regard, the problem of ensuring security in cyberspace is particularly relevant in modern society. First of all, Internet addiction manifests itself in the fact that people, spending a lot of time on the Internet, forget about their responsibilities and real problems. Unlimited use of computers and the Internet is especially dangerous for children and young people. A large amount of time spent at a computer monitor leads to excessive visual stress and, as a result, to the development of myopia. There are also problems with digestion, headaches, and impaired concentration of attention. Speaking of the latter, we can note the fact that almost any Internet resource is organized on the principle of "read this and see what else is available." Mostly sites show bright graphic ads that make you draw the attention of any person, even with an iron mind. As a result, attention becomes more distracted than it was before. Another of the most dangerous consequences is the limited emotional contact and communication with family and friends in real life, which leads to a number of psychological problems. Of course, the Internet also has a positive meaning. For example, it promotes both educational and intellectual development: there are a variety of sites for parents that contain valuable material for raising and teaching children (online educational online games, interactive textbooks, drawing lessons, English, etc.)

Many sociologists consider the issue of Internet addiction in terms of its impact on the socialization of a teenager. Thanks to The Internet creates all the conditions for earlier inclusion of an individual in social activities. People who live their life on the Internet often need social support, they have great difficulties in communicating, they experience dissatisfaction, low self-esteem, complexities, shyness and a number of other possible problems of this kind. Unfortunately, the Internet is able to solve almost all such problems, providing a virtual life (where you can make yourself absolutely anyone, that is, realize all your dreams of your own exclusivity) instead of a real life, to which such a person simply turns out to be unsuitable. Practice shows that such people are in a hurry to go to a safe environment for them, to a life where they have no obligations. Over time, this way of life and thinking permeates all levels of their reality, and the result is that a person acts, lives and thinks completely differently. The approach to solving various life problems is changing.

Several types of manifestation Internet addictions:

virtual Dating - redundancy of acquaintances and friends in the network, constant newacquaintances;

obsessive need for the network - playing online gambling, constant purchases or participation in auctions, participation in various discussions onforums;

endlesstravelontheweb-searchforinformationindatabasesandsearchsites;

gambling addiction - an obsessive game of online computergames.

List of psychological symptoms that may occur in a person at risk for Internetaddiction:

- feeling of well-being, and sometimes even euphoria from being at the computer;
- problematic, and in some cases, the inability to interruptwork;
- increase the amount of time spent on the monitorscreen;
- inattentive attitude towards family members and friends, turning into complete disregard andindifference;
- feelings of internal discomfort, emptiness, depression, and irritation that occur in the absence of acomputer;
- more frequent lies to employers and family members about theiractivities;
- the occurrence of problems with work orstudy.

A number of the following characteristics of communication on the Internet and its benefits and disadvantages are highlighted:

In online communication nonverbal means of communication lose their meaning. Of course, there is a set of "emoticons" that represent a number of emotions, but this is not an equal equivalent. In other words, a person can not adequately assess the opponent because of his physical unrepresentation.

Anonymous nature of communication. Anonymity allows self-presentation of a teenager and young people , based not only on their psychological characteristics, but also allowing them to create a different image, significantly different from the previous one. a realone.

Consider the advantages of the Internet. There are such opportunities as earning money online, a way to show, prove yourself by placing your own page or written programs, and so on. You can also use the Internet to find jobs and old friends you haven't seen in a longtime.

On the Internet, everyone makes their own way. You decide which network services to use. There are programs on the Internet that solve a certain range of tasks. With it, you can even make phone calls, make purchases, book flights and hotel rooms, advertise your products and businesses, communicate in a variety of ways, make friends and even fall in love, and this is not all.

Millions of disabled people also got the opportunity to work remotely and communicate with friends. There are huge libraries of all kinds of literature on the Internet, first of all, scientific literature is valuable – since ordinary books cost a lot of money, and many scientists, unfortunately, are not able to provide themselves with the necessary literature, the Internet gives them such an opportunity. Also, the Internet is truly the largest collection of information, the Internet gives you the opportunity to learn a lot, get a profession, or raise your skills to a different level. Also on the Internet, you can always get the latest news on a narrow or broad topic.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

The possibilities of the Internet are almost limitless, the only thing that the global network can never replace is the charms of live communication, the charms of letters written by the hand of a friend or loved one, and sitting in front of a flickering screen you will never be able to go for a walk with friends in real life. This, of course, is a big drawback of the network, but at the same time it is a great advantage, because you can't move to virtual reality forever, after all, we are real people, not machines.

However, we can identify positive factors in the use of the Internet by modern teenagers:

- the emergence of interest in school subjects,
- active use of scientific and technical information in training,
- relief of tension,
- contribute to the aesthetic education,
- new ways to organize your time are being developed,
- ability to plan your activities.

In turn, the positive aspects include expanding the circle of communication, raising awareness in certain areas, as well as overcoming the communication deficit. The fact that the world wide web is an indispensable assistant in your studies. Young people will find information of interest to them, will be able to make an abstract, make a synopsis. Without leaving the house, the child can get acquainted with the sights of the whole world, historical events, and watch documentaries. The development and ability to use the Internet and computer equipment is appreciated, as progress does not stand still, and in the future these skills will be useful for the child to work.

It was also noted that The Internet as a means of "escaping" from reality reveals the following possibilities:

- the possibility of anonymous, social communication (here the sense of security in its implementation is of particular importance);
- the ability to create and realize fantasies (including the ability to create new images of the " I " that cannot be realized in real life (for example, role-playing

games.);

- unlimited access to information, "informational vampirism" (the key point is that the main danger is faced by people who can not imagine their life without the Internet and do not know how to build relationships in real life);
- a wide opportunity to search for an interlocutor based on a number of criteria, which is often impossible in real life (it is important to note here that there is no need to hold the attention of one interlocutor, since you can communicate with several at once).

It's also worth noting that The Internet provides great opportunities not only in the field of communication, but also in access to resources with information. One of the features The advantage of the Internet is that there are no restrictions on obtaining any kind of information. However, the lack of access to resources The Internet is fraught with serious potential dangers for humans. The global network contains a large number of resources that demonstrate and promote various forms of violence, popularize various methods of mind manipulation, inculcate mysticism, racism, sexism, and so on.

The negative is that the Internet gives the illusion of permissiveness, pulling out of us the worst that is in us. And what? After all, everything is possible! There are suicide clubs, drug addicts ' clubs, and clubs that train novice terrorists on the Internet. In such clubs, you can order your own death, buy a couple of sticks of dynamite, learn how to properly pick up and inject drugs.

But children absorb information like a sponge - and what do they get from the Internet? Just go to some sites and you will understand everything for yourself. Hackers have appeared on the Internet, destroying everything in their path for the sake of satisfying their hurt ego, they can not create, they can only destroy. But let's think about what motivated them to destroy everything and everything on the Internet? Not a walk on it? Unfortunately, the negative information on the Internet at the moment prevails. Long-term computer work negatively affects many functions of our body: higher nervous activity, endocrine, immune and reproductive systems, vision and the human musculoskeletal system.

But, if vision and hearing can be damaged through the keyboard, "mouse" or monitor, then the psyche is primarily affected by virtual things, so to speak - games and the Internet. This is something that is "addictive", something that is impossible to break away from, something that many people can no longer imagine their life without - this is a manic addiction to the Internet or games. People who live their lives on the Internet often need social support, they have great difficulties in communicating, they experience dissatisfaction, low self-esteem, complexities, shyness. They go to a safe

environment for them, a non-binding life. Thus, they, firstly, aggravate those character traits that they would like to get rid of, and also acquire new ones: escape from reality by changing their mental state, virtually changing their gender and age... Of course, gradually this way of life, this way of thinking, permeates all levels of their life. The person begins to act and think differently. It differently solve domestic issues, family, personal, professional, partnership, etc.

Negative factors of using the Internet by teenagers:

- danger of suppressing interpersonal communication,
- danger of reducing the role of oral and written speech,
- weakening of the ability to independent creative thinking,
- harmful effects on the psyche,
- danger of reducing the socialization of a teenager.

Unfortunately, the Internet has started to grow the number of different communities that can affect the mental state of adolescents and young people, their mood, provoke rash actions.

CONCLUSION.

Deterioration of the child's vision and posture are the main negative consequences of frequent computer sitting. Every year, the number of people complaining about their eyesight is growing, so it is up to parents to monitor the time spent by their child at the computer monitor.

Summing up the above, we can say that The Internet has become very important in modern society. According to the rules of modern society, it is almost impossible to exist without using Internet resources. Internet use is a global time saver, but there is no denying that excessive Internet use can affect our psyche. No wonder there is such a saying: "everything is good in moderation. And the Internet can do good and harm, but you need to be able to balance. Teenagers and young people need to create a framework for using the Internet, determine the amount of time spent in the virtual world.

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